

Impact of Macro Environmental Factors on the Sustainable Development of Zambia Copper Mining Industry

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Abstract: Zambia is regarded as a mining country because the country's economy has always been largely supported by copper mining. However, the performance of the Zambian copper mining industry is negatively affected by macro-environmental factors, and thus sustainability in the sector is also threatened. The purpose of this research is to determine, analyze the macro environmental factors and make recommendations for the good performance of the Zambian copper mining industry. Politic, Economic, Social, Technology, Environment, and Social (PESTEL), External Factor Analysis Summary (EFAS) and Strength, Weakness, Opportunity, and Threat (SWOT) methods were adopted for this study. The results showed that the macro environmental factors to be improved are in the political, economic, social, technological, legal and environmental domains. Thus, these improved factors, the performance of the copper mining industry will be improved and the sustainable development will be ensured.

Keywords: Zambia; copper; mining industry; macro environmental; performance; sustainable development

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1. Introduction

Given that the current external business environment is marked by a high level of unpredictability, complexity, and dynamism, the research is relevant. The capacity of the industry to adapt to changes in the external environment, or the ability of the industry to recognize environmental changes and successfully respond to them, is one of the requirements for the survival of the industry and its development [1].

The first step in strategic management is the study of the external environment since it serves as the foundation for figuring out the organization's mission and goals, as well as for creating behavioral strategies that will help it accomplish these goals. It provides time to anticipate opportunities, make plans for unforeseen events, create an early warning system for potential threats, and create strategies that can transform past threats into a variety of lucrative opportunities.

A methodical approach to the development of the company's competitive conduct includes the determination of positions in the external environment.

The external environment of the business is a collection of elements (situations and entities) that have an impact on the operations of the industry [2]. The external environment is divided into factors of indirect (macro environment) and direct (microenvironment) effects [3]. The macro environment include factors characterizing the development of the national economy as a whole, which factors include the pillars of sustainable development [4].

The political factor refers to variables that affect how political processes evolve, the stability of legal standards in a country's economy, the political ideology that guides government policy, the level of public dissatisfaction with the government, etc [5]. Economic environment refers to variables that affect how economic processes develop in the national economy (GDP growth rates, external debts, etc.), how the state budget and tax policy affect the population's financial security, how appealing the national economy is to investors, how stable the national currency is, how much inflation there is, how high the tax rates are, etc. [6]. The social factor includes factors that affect the population's growth rates, demographics, and demographic structures as well as development patterns. It also includes factors that affect people's attitudes toward employment and quality of life [7]. The status of the job market and the population of healthy individuals are greatly influenced by the social environment. Certain marketplaces for products or services may be impacted by changes in the social environment. The technical factor (methods of converting resources into output) includes components that define the development patterns of scientific and technological advancement and the changes in the technological basis of production that go along with them [8]. The environmental factor involves all the elements determining the protection, preservation and reclamation of the environment [9]. The legal factor involves the laws governing the activities and operations of the industry [10].

The complexity of the external environment is one of several variables to which businesses must adapt [11]. The environment's mobility refers to how quickly things change in the business environment [12]. According to many experts and managers, the external environment of businesses is changing more quickly than ever in the modern day and there are certain industries whose external environment is particularly mobile [13].

The degree of uncertainty in the external environment depends on both how much knowledge an organization has about a particular element and how confident it is in the accuracy of that knowledge [14]. The environment is more uncertain when there is insufficient information or when there are some errors or questions about its provenance than when there is sufficient information and there are good reasons to believe that it is reasonable and highly dependable [15].

There are factors that cannot be managed by one enterprise. In this sense, it is crucial to act quickly in response to any changes in the environment. Responsiveness of the external environment is determined by a number of concepts that will be discussed below. The degree to which a change in one environmental component has an impact on other ones is known as their interconnectedness. The complexity of the external environment is the number of factors to which companies must react, as well as the variability of each factor [16].

In this study, we examine the influence of macro-environmental factors on the performance of the copper mining industry in Zambia. The main techniques for diagnosing the external environment of the copper mining industry in Zambia are reviewed, enabling the analysis of the macro environment of the industry and drawing conclusions regarding its competitive position and contribution to sustainable development, which are the most significant results, related to scientific novelty. The practical implementation mechanism of the methodologies and a set of managerial choices to reduce the hazards likely to develop are proposed.

1.1. Literature review

There are a number of macro-environmental factors facing industries in general and mining industries in particular. They generally encompass factors related to politics, economics, social, technology, environment, legal. This section presents some learning materials and methods related to our proposed study. Macro-environmental factor assessment methods can be applied in a variety of industries due to their excellent assessment capabilities.

According to World Bank [17] most sub-sahara African industries are underperforming due to macro-environmental challenges, what makes our study necessary and relevant. The World bank [18] showed how can Zambia Benefit More from Mining. The World Bank [19] showed how make mining work for Zambia. In these last two articles, the World Bank has shown in a superficial way how the performance of Zambian copper could be revised upwards, but our study has contributed more to this by showing in a broader way the factors and subfactors being at the origin of the underperformance of the industry.

Mancini and Sala [20] conducted a review of the associated literature and showed in their study that, although mining provides essential inputs to the functioning of economies, it can at the same time generate social and environmental impacts that could include the acceptance of the sector by the public, which will have a negative impact on the business and the revenues of the mining industry.

Frederiksen in [21] applied a political settlements approach to examine the political effects of corporate social responsibility in mining in developing countries, the case of Zambia. This politico-social factor generates consistent economic results for the country in question and improves the image of the mining company, which has a long-term impact on the revenues of the mining company. Frederiksen's study was exclusively limited to political and social factors, it contributed to our study on these two factors, but we extended it by adding economic, technological, environmental and legal factors.

Kim et al. (2019) in [22] applied data mining and sentence level classification to analyze business environmental. this article gave us the basic knowledge on the analysis of the macro environment of the mining industry, which is the subject of our study

Morgunova and Bolkina in [2] displayed the large-scale environmental elements influencing the competitiveness of an industrial company's commercial operations. The study reveals that the competitiveness of a company must be based on such intangible assets that fully take into account the influence and change of the external environment.

Gabriel and Juan in [23] examined the macro environmental elements that affect the growth of the electric and hybrid sector using the PESTEL framework, highlighting possibilities and challenges presented by its macro environment. This article showed us how the PESTEL method is applied to study the macro environment of an industry, our study corroborates it by adding EFAS and SWOT methods.

Shabanova et al. in [24] demonstrated that PESTEL and SWOT analyses may disclose the industry's strengths as well as its flaws, as well as help the industry recognize immediate threats, operate more effectively, and improve its competitive position.

Nikolaou and Evangelinos in [25], used SWOT analysis to examine the challenges faced by Greek mining and mineral industry. This study applies the SWOT method only, in ours we show the origin of the SWOT factors by PESTEL and EFAS methods and the sub factors are scored. This makes it possible to deal effectively with the challenges facing the industry.

For the best performance of the Zambian copper mining industry, the notion of sustainable development must be well applied in the mining field. The notion of "sustainable development" is increasingly frequently used to describe development issues [26]. sustainable development was defined as the "ability to make development sustainable—to ensure that it meets the needs of the present without compromising the ability of future generations to meet their own needs" [27]. This, however, doing so requires that economic, environmental, and social considerations be taken into account and integrated into all decision-making processes [28].

The United Nations (UN) accepted the sustainable development agenda, a worldwide, integrated, and human rights-based effort, in 2015. It highlights how development, social justice, and the environment are interconnected. The 17 associated Sustainable Development Goals have a wider and far more varied reach than the millennium development goals (MDG), which were well-known from 2000 to 2015 [29]. The sustainable development goals are a collection of 17 global goals that include 169 ambitious targets and roughly 230 indicators. [30]. The global goals serve as the consensus worldwide action plan for economic development that is fair, socially inclusive, and ecologically sustainable.

In the African context, achieving community development means integrating the Sustainable Development Goals into regional developmental plans such as the African Mining Vision, a continental policy for sustainable resource development and the African Agenda 2063 [31]. The latter aims to solve the numerous difficulties posed by fully using Africa's mineral riches in order to promote sustainable development. The African Mining Vision (AMV) also aims to promote socioeconomic development and broad-based sustainable growth via the transparent, just, and efficient utilization of Africa's natural resources. Therefore, it is necessary for African Union (AU) member states, of which Zambia is a member, to completely implement the AMV and, in accordance with the framework's rules, to integrate it with national mining sector policies. This initiative is expected to help Africa achieve the Sustainable Development Goals and other regional objectives [32].

The literature above allows us to know how to apply the methods used in our study and show us that no particular study on the impact of macro environmental factors on the performance of the copper mining industry has so far been made.

Based in literature presented above, this paper takes Zambia copper mining industry as a case study, with the following objectives:

- (1) Identify the strengths of Zambia copper mining industry, so that the industry can take advantages of them.
- (2) Identify weaknesses in the Zambia copper mining industry, so that the industry can address them.
- (3) Identify the opportunities that arise in the Zambia mining industry, so that the industry can take advantage of them.
- (4) Identify threats to the Zambia copper mining industry, so that the industry can prevent them.

These objectives will be achieved using the PESTEL and EFAS method, which methods make it possible to highlight the strengths, weaknesses, opportunities and threats by the SWOT method.

1.2. Conceptual framework

Conceptual framework is a diagrammatic presentation of the relationship between dependent and independent variables as shown in Figure 1. In this study, the dependent variable is performance of Zambia copper mining industry while independent variables are political factors, economic factors, social factors, technological factors, environmental factors and legal factors.

Fig. 1: Conceptual framework

2. Materials and Methods

PESTEL, FAS, and SWOT were used to identify the key Zambia copper mining industry’s macro environmental factors that are taken into account in determining the performance of the industry.

PESTEL analysis is a quick and easy procedure [33]. It is a method for long-term strategic planning that offers projections for the next three to five years together with an annual information update. The name of this technique is an acronym of six parameters of the enterprise external environment: P - Political factor; E - Economical factor; S - Social factor; T - Technological factor; E – Environment; L – Legal as illustrated in Figure 2.

Fig. 2: The factors covered by PESTEL analysis

PESTEL depends so much on interpretation, which is extremely arbitrary. This analysis should be carried out by a highly competent specialist who is capable of independently reviewing all relevant parts of the external environment [34].

The outcomes of the examination of strategic environmental elements are summarized using EFAS analysis or External Factor Analysis Summary.

The next type of analysis under consideration is SWOT analysis. SWOT stands for Strengths (S), Weaknesses (W), Opportunities (O), and Threats (T) [35], as shown in Figure 3.

Fig. 3: The factors covered by SWOT analysis

SWOT analysis is now the most popular technique in global management practice for creating plans for the growth of businesses and other forms of economic activity based on an examination of the internal and external economic environment [36]. The analysis of resources, the assessment of resource use potential, the choice of goals and objectives, and the examination of the external environment to spot opportunities and dangers are all part of this strategy. Knowing your strengths will help to take advantage of market opportunities and avoid dangers; identifying your weaknesses will help to construct protection in a timely manner and plan measures to reduce them [37].

This kind of study is employed to evaluate the enterprise's internal and external environments. It entails the capacity to evaluate the company's current status and strategic possibilities, which is attained by research into the company's strengths and weaknesses, market opportunities, and threats factors. The internal situation of the company is reflected in S and W, and the external environment is reflected in O and T. SWOT analysis has managerial and strategic relevance if it integrates internal and external environment elements and identifies the opportunities and resources the organization will require in the future [24].

The PESTEL factors are related to SWOT factors in order to develop a framework as shown in Figure 3. Depending on the results, the PESTEL factor may manifest as favorable or unfavorable; for example, a conducive political situation is strength while an unconducive situation is a threat.

Fig. 4: Showing the relationship between PESTEL and SWOT factors framework.

3. Results

3.1. Qualitative PESTEL analysis

The main PESTEL factors do not enable detailed analysis of the macro environment, therefore the initial stage that was carried out in the PESTEL analysis was identified of relevant sub-factors. Clusters of sub-factors are identified as indicated in Table 1.

Tab. 1: Identified PESTEL sub-factors affecting the performance of Zambia copper mining industry

PESTEL factor	Identified sub-factors	PESTEL factor	Identified sub-factors
Political (P)	P1: Political stability	Economic (E)	E1: Inconsistency in mining taxes
	P2: Lack of transparency		E2: Inflation
	P3: Trade restriction and reforms		E3: Exchange rates
	P4: Fiscal policies		E4: Continuing crisis in the Zambian economy
Social (S)	S1: Outflow of economically active population from the regions	Technological (T)	T1: Lack of infrastructure
	S2: Improvements in urban infrastructure		T2: Lack of geological mapping and survey
	S3: Improving the company's image in the eye of the population		T3: Insufficient energy
	S4: Corporate social responsibility		T4: Lack of research and development

Environmental (E)	E1: Insufficient treatment	Legal (L)	L1: Mining Act and policies
	E2: Reclamation policies		L2: Taxation
	E3: Consistent environmental expertise		L3: Import and export policies
			L4: Border crossing regulations
			L5: Technology legislation

3.2. Quantitative PESTEL analysis

A survey was conducted in Lusaka, the capital city of Zambia. A questionnaire is developed based on Table 1. A face validation of the questionnaire was done involving three selected experts. The respondents were asked to rate each sub-factor on an integer scale ranging, where a higher score indicates a better environment to the good performance. Twenty-four representatives from large copper mining companies and institutions related to mining were identified. Twenty-one responses were received and an average rate for each sub-factor was calculated. The ratings from the twenty-one responses were computed. The results of quantitative PESTEL analysis of Zambia copper mining industry are given in Table 2.

Tab. 2: Quantitative PESTEL analysis results

PESTEL factor	sub-industry	Significance for the industry	Impact on the Enterprise	Direction of Influence	Degree of significance
		X	Y	Z	$S=X*Y*Z$
P ₁		3	3	+1	+9
P ₂		2	1	-1	-3
P ₃		3	2	+1	+6
P ₄		3	3	-1	-9
E ₁		3	3	-1	-9
E ₂		2	2	-1	-4
E ₃		2	2	-1	-4
E ₄		1	3	-1	-3
S ₁		2	2	-1	-4
S ₂		2	2	+1	+4
S ₃		2	2	+1	+4
S ₄		2	1	+1	+2
T ₁		2	2	-1	-4
T ₂		2	3	-1	-6
T ₃		3	2	-1	-6
T ₄		2	3	-1	-6
E ₁		1	3	-1	-3
E ₂		1	1	-1	-1
E ₃		1	1	-1	-1

L ₁	3	2	+1	+6
L ₂	3	3	-1	-9
L ₃	2	2	+1	+4
L ₄	1	2	+1	+2
L ₅	3	2	+1	+6

3.3. EFAS

EFAS is External Factor Analysis Summary by weighting and rating opportunities and threats. So that we can determine the total score of opportunities and threats. The results of EFAS for Zambia copper mining industry are given in Table 3.

Tab. 3: EFAS results for Zambia copper mining industry

External factors	strategic	Weight	Score	Weighted score
Opportunities				
P1: Political stability		0.2	4	0.8
P3: Trade restriction and reforms		0.18	4	0.72
S2: Improvements in urban infrastructure		0.1	3	0.3
S3: Improving the company's image in the eye of the population		0.1	4	0.4
S4: Corporate social responsibility		0.06	3	0.18
L1: Mining Act and policies		0.06	3	0.18
L3: Import and export policies		0.05	3	0.15
L4: Border crossing regulations		0.05	3	0.15
L5: Technology legislation		0.05	3	0.15
Threats				
P2: Lack of transparency		0.01	4	0.04
P4: Fiscal policies		0.01	4	0.04
E1: Inconsistency in mining taxes		0.01	4	0.04
E2: Inflation		0.01	3	0.03
E3: Exchange rates		0.01	3	0.03

E4: Continuing crisis in the Zambian economy	0.01	1	0.01
S1: Outflow of economically active population from the regions	0.01	1	0.01
T1: Lack of infrastructure	0.01	3	0.03
T2: Lack of geological mapping and survey	0.01	3	0.03
T3: Insufficient energy	0.01	3	0.03
T4: Lack of research and development	0.01	2	0.02
L2: Taxation	0.01	4	0.04
E1: Insufficient treatment of waste	0.01	1	0.01
E2: Lack of strict reclamation policies	0.01	1	0.01
E3: Lack of consistent environment expertise	0.01	1	0.01
Summary Score	1		3.41

3.4. SWOT analysis

SWOT analysis enables a thorough evaluation of the industry's position in the market. SWOT framework is used as a matrix with external and internal environmental factors. Table 4 lists the findings of the SWOT analysis for Zambia copper mining industry.

Tab. 4: SWOT analysis showing macro environmental factors affecting performance of Zambia copper mining industry

Factors	
Strengths	Weaknesses
Stability of politic	Low corruption index
Open trade policy	Inadequate budgetary management and transparency
Low living costs	Negative attitude at work
Workforce accessibility	Ineffective legal system
Adequate socioeconomic and labor laws and policies	Mining equipment outdated
	Inadequate infrastructure
	Insufficient vital services
	Inadequate environmental protection

Opportunities

Geographically advantageous site

Pleasant weather

Threats

Changes in tax regime on a regular basis

An unpredictably fluctuating foreign currency rate

No mining innovation

4. Discussion

The macro environmental factors play a key role in industry performance. For example, Chile is a developing country like Zambia whose economy is largely based on copper mining industry like Zambia. Chile faces a significant risk posed by its set of operations that do not respond to sustainable development. To achieve the expected production increases, improve competitiveness in the global market, Chile is called upon to significantly improve the macro environment economically, technologically and environmentally [38].

In our study, the qualitative analysis is conducted using the PESTEL method to highlight the key sub-factors that constitute the macro environment of the Zambian copper industry. From this qualitative analysis, the quantitative analysis is carried out to give the score to each sub factor and thus the significance of each sub actor is released. After consolidating the results, PESTEL analysis showed that the sub-factors that are less ranked and the well-ranked are in all groups of factors namely political, economic, social, technological, legal and environmental.

In the political domain, Zambia has political stability and open trade policies, but needs to improve on its corruption index, transparency, and management of national resources.

In economic domain, the lack of policy around the implementation of the tax and unstable foreign exchange rate may affect investment attractiveness into the mining sector.

In social domain, admittedly, mining companies participate in the development of local communities, particularly in urban infrastructure. However, there is a mismatch in the priorities of the mining industry and that of the communities. This has direct repercussions on sustainable development and consequently when the local population is not satisfied, the performance of the copper mining industry is threatened especially since the mining companies need the services of the local population. It would be better if it had a framework involving all stakeholders in order to jointly decide on the social areas to be supported.

In technological domain, Zambia has a low rating. This is because of lack of geological mapping and survey, insufficient energy, and lack of research and development. In the industrial field, if the technology is not advanced, directly the industrial performance will be at a low level. Thus, the income will not be as it should be and therefore the sustainable development, which needs money from the mining industry, will not be well applied. Evidence shows that encouraging technological advancement, research and innovation as well as infrastructural development are three key factors in generating economic growth and sustainable development [39].

In environmental domain, environmental protection is not applied, due to insufficient treatment, lack of reclamation policies and consistent environmental expertise. Environmental protection is not guaranteed. This is explained by the insufficient treatment, lack of reclamation policies and lack of consistent environmental expertise, which is threatening for sustainable development.

In legal domain, generally, the Zambian mining law has had a good mark except the tax law, which always creates conflicts between the government and the mining companies, and this law is often amended.

EFAS classified all macro environmental sub-factors into two groups namely opportunities and threats. The advantageous sub-factors for the Zambian copper mining industry are opportunities and the disadvantageous sub-factors are threats. Each EFAS factor is weighed and assigned a score. The weighted score is obtained by multiplying

the weight and the score; and thus the impact of each factor of the EFAS is released. EFAS shows the impact of opportunities and threats facing the industry. The magnitude of the impact is not the same for all factors.

SWOT analysis has revealed the strengths and weaknesses as well as the opportunities and threats facing the Zambian copper mining industry. The strengths consist of stability of politic, open trade policy, low living costs, workforce accessibility and adequate socioeconomic and labor policies. The weaknesses are low corruption index, inadequate budgetary management and transparency, negative attitude at work, ineffective legal system, mining equipment outdated, inadequate infrastructure, insufficient vital services and inadequate environmental protection as for the opportunities, they are composed of geographically advantageous site and pleasant weather. The threats include changes in tax regime on a regular basis, an unpredictably fluctuating foreign currency rate and no mining innovation. The Zambian copper mining industry should address its weaknesses and capitalize on its strengths and opportunities to achieve better performance and sustainable development.

5. Conclusion

The fate of industrial enterprises in a contemporary economy largely depends on their adaptation to the market [40]. A complex open socio-economic system established for specific purposes and supported by a variety of environmental conditions is known as an industrial enterprise [41]. Existing threats in the outside world and avoiding them is a process of adaptation [42]. The correct adaptation of the industry will have a major impact on performance, in particular on sustainable development.

Our study is relevant to the Zambian community, especially since it shows how the Zambian copper industry could perform efficiently, and thus contribute considerably to sustainable development, especially since copper production is the economic pillar of the Zambia.

Macro environmental factors are categorized in various ways and in accordance with various guiding principles because of their diversity. Our study classified the sub-factors into six groups of factors namely political, economic, social, technological, environmental and legal. However, the classification of variables used and often followed in management is that of direct and indirect effect factors. The study found that the factors, which are advantageous and disadvantageous for the copper mining industry in Zambia, are distributed in the six groups of factors.

The study found that the industry's ability to operate effectively depends on building distinct capabilities that enable the industry to address its weaknesses and prevent threats, while capitalizing on its strengths and opportunities to achieve new better performance, and thus contribute effectively to sustainable development.

The list of sub-factors of the PESTEL, FAS and SWOT methods could be longer than those we have compiled in our study. We have identified key sub-factors. Thus, we recommend further studies in the future, which may be more exhaustive for more contributions to the sustainable development of Zambia's copper mining industry.

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